

AN IMPROVED LOOSE BUNDLE TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF WEIBULL PARAMETERS

Mohamed R'Mili and Paul Merle

Groupe d'Etudes de Métallurgie Physique et de Physique des Matériaux-URA CNRS 341
Institut National des Sciences Appliquées, 69621 Villeurbanne-Cedex, France

ABSTRACT

The statistical parameters (Weibull shape parameter, average strength) of carbon fibers have been measured using monofilaments or bundles. Bundles were prepared so as to measure their strain directly. Comparison between the two methods show that the bundle technique allows us to obtain sound values of the Weibull parameters of the reinforcement and also to measure the minimum rupture strain of the fibers. This method was applied to the study of B₄C coated or non coated T300 carbon fibers. The results were used to understand the comparative mechanical behaviour of metal matrix composites elaborated with these materials

INTRODUCTION

The rupture strength of unidirectional metal matrix composites is essentially dependant of the mechanical behaviour of the reinforcement. The evaluation of this mechanical property thus requires the knowledge of the mechanical characteristics of the fibers. These are usually determined by individually testing a sample of about 40 fibers so as to measure their individual strength and thus to estimate the parameters of the associated Weibull strength distribution. Another method, based on the study of the rupture of a bundle of fibers, assuming a spatial random distribution of the individual failures of fibers, was initially developed by Daniels [1] and Coleman [2] and later used by Manders and Chou [3] for carbon and glass fibers and also by Chi et al.[4] for carbon fibers. This technique has also been used recently by Evans et al.[5] and Cowking et al.[6] for glass fibers. It must however be underlined that, in these studies, experimental difficulties made it difficult to measure the true strain of the bundle, which was generally calculated using the displacement of the crosshead of the testing machine. Moreover, the number N_1 of initially loaded fibers was generally measured from direct microscopy examination or acoustic emission, but this gives an imprecise value of N_1 . We thus tried to set up an experimental method allowing us to overcome these difficulties so as to obtain more reliable values of Weibull parameters.

METHODOLOGY

Tensile test on monofilaments were performed so as to obtain results which could be compared to those obtained on monobundles. The individual fiber strength distribution was analyzed by the two-parameter Weibull model [7]. These parameters were determined using classical tension tests on a number n of individual fibers ($n > 40$).

According to this model the cumulative probability $F_q(\sigma)$ of failure in the interval $[0, \sigma]$ may be written, for a sample of gauge length L :

$$F_q(\sigma) = 1 - \exp[-L(\sigma/\sigma_0)^m] \tag{1}$$

where m is the Weibull modulus and σ_0 an intrinsic characteristic of the material. The Weibull parameters m and σ_0 were determined in the classical way using the least square method applied to the linear plot $\text{Ln}\sigma - \text{Ln}[\text{Ln}\{1/(1-F_q)\}]$. The mean strength of the distribution, given by :

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \sigma_0 L^{-1/m} \Gamma(1+1/m) \tag{2}$$

where Γ represents the Gamma function, was then deduced from these measurements.

Figure 1 Typical P-ε curve

Assuming a random and individual failure of fibers in the bundle, Manders and Chou [4] and Chi et al. [4] have shown that the behaviour of this bundle may be described using the Weibull parameters of the individual fibers and their geometrical characteristics. Assuming also that the applied load is uniformly distributed among the surviving fibers, the load at an applied strain ϵ during a bundle tensile test may be written

$$P = A N_1 E_f \epsilon \exp[-(\epsilon / \epsilon_L)^m] \tag{3}$$

where A is the value of the cross area of the fibers, E_f their modulus, N_1 the number of initially loaded fibers and $\epsilon_L = \sigma_L / E_f$ a strain scale coefficient. Relation (3) will be called the P-ε relation.

We can thus determine the Weibull parameters of the fibre from tension tests experiments on bundles. The experimental procedure is the following [4] :

-Experimental determination of the P-ε curve of the bundle. (Figure 1). In our case, the experimental device allows us to measure the bundle strain directly.

-Determination of the number N_1 of initially loaded fibers from the initial slope S_0 of the P- ϵ curve. Indeed

$$N_1 = S_0 / A E_f \quad (4)$$

As the true value of S_0 is obtained experimentally, this determination only needs a precise knowledge of the tensile modulus of the fibers

-Determination of the Weibull shape parameter m from S_0 and S^* . This last value is the slope of the straight line defined by the origin of the P- ϵ curve and the point corresponding to the maximal load (Figure 1).

$$1/m = \text{Ln} (S_0/S^*) \quad (5)$$

-Calculation of the average strength of the fibers for the gauge length used :

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = P^*(2.72 m)^{1/m} \Gamma(1+1/m) / N_1 A \quad (6)$$

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

The single filament and loose bundle tension tests were performed on Thornel-300-6K carbon fibers (noted T300) and on the same fibers with a B4C coating (noted T300-B4C) obtained by a reactive chemical vapor deposition process [8] (RCVD). The mean coating thickness is about 50 nm, the mean fiber diameter being about 7 μ m.

Weibull parameters of monofilaments have been determined according to the experimental procedure described above. Figure 2 represents a typical plot of strength distribution and the results are given in table 1. It may be underlined that results for T300 and T300-B4C fibers are, for a gauge length of 30 mm, very similar. For a gauge length of 60mm, we observe a rather large difference between the m values (7.6 for T300 fibers and 3.7 for T300-B4C fibers). This discrepancy may be attributed to the problems arising from the selection of a representative population of long fibers.

Figure 2 Strength distributions determined by single fiber tests with 30mm gauge length

The characterisation of the strength distribution of the reinforcement using monobundle tests needs a precise determination of Young's modulus of the fibers. This has been determined from

tension tests on monofilaments. However, as in these tests, the strain is deduced from the value of the displacement of the testing machine crosshead, a direct estimation from the load-displacement curve of a monofilament sample leads to an underestimated value of E_f . This value is only about 90% of that obtained either by a direct measure with an optic sensor or by an indirect evaluation taking into account the deformation of the apparatus.

Fibers	Gauge length (mm)	Test number	m	$\langle \sigma \rangle$ (MPa)
T300	30	100	5,5	2950
	60	50	7,6	2700
T300-B4C	30	50	5,4	2930
	60	50	3,7	2750

Table 1 Weibull parameters estimated from single filament tests

Young's modulus may thus be precisely determined using the evolution of the compliance of the whole system, $C = \Delta l / P$, where Δl is the total displacement of the cross head of the machine, with the ratio L/A , where L is the gauge length and A the section area of the fiber. Indeed, we may write :

$$C = (L/A E_f) + C_e \tag{7}$$

where C_e is the compliance of the testing device. The plot of C versus L/A (Figure 3) thus allows us to determine Young's modulus of the fibers and the compliance of the device system.

Figure 3 Young's modulus of T300 fibers determined from the variation of compliance with the gauge length of the fibers

The obtention of bundles with aligned and independent fibers is the major difficulty encountered in the preparation of samples for bundle tests. A special system has been set up for this purpose.

It also allows us to obtain specimens with a well defined gauge length and at the same time allows us to fix a mechanic extensometer for a direct measurement of the sample deformation

A bundle of about 100mm long is necessary for the preparation of samples of 30mm gauge length. These bundles are hung from one of their ends, the other remaining free. A lubricant is then used to align the filaments and to make the handling of the bundle easier. Two small thermo-retractable stumps of 2mm long are threaded on the bundle so as to define the gauge length and to allow the fixation of the extensometer. The bundle is then cured at 100°C for a few seconds in order for the stumps to retract and to clamp the fibers. The sample heads are made with two thermo-retractable pieces of about 20 mm long which are threaded at the free ends of the sample. An epoxy resin is then injected with a syringe in these thermo-retractable tubes which are heated so as to clamp the fibers.

Typical P-ε curves obtained in the case of a T300 and a T300-B4C bundle are shown in figure 4. These curves have been chosen so that the number of initially loaded fibers is equivalent for the two bundles (identical load-strain slope at the origin). It can be observed that these curves exhibit a well-defined maximum showing that the failure of the bundle is of a controlled type

Figure 4 Comparison between P-ε curves of T300 and T300-B4C fibers

Moreover, a regular deviation from the linear behaviour is observed at a certain strain value. This shows that fibers effectively fail in an individual and random way, which proves that the assumptions of the theoretical model are rather well verified in the experimental conditions. It must be underlined that the failure of bundles has never been observed near their ends, which confirms the absence of stress concentrations on the bundle due to the fixation system. However, some differences appear between the two curves:

- The strain ϵ_0 corresponding to the beginning of the fibers failure and the ultimate load are much lower for the coated than for the non-coated fibers.

- A wider maximum is observed for T300-B4C samples.

Table 2 gives the results on Weibull parameters obtained on T300 and T300-B4C monobundles of 30mm and 60 mm gauge length and also on specific data of the experiment (N_1 , ϵ^* , ϵ_0). It can be observed that:

The number of fibers initially loaded is less than the total number of the fibers in the bundle. This difference could be due to the failure of monofilaments during the preparation of the specimen.

In spite of the fact that the value of the maximum load is lower in the case of coated fibers, the $\langle\sigma\rangle$ values obtained for the two kinds of fibers are not very different. Indeed, the earlier rupture of coated fibers leads to a lower number of surviving fibers at the maximum load.

Fibers	N_1	Gauge Length (mm)	Test number	m	$\langle\sigma\rangle$ (MPa)	ε^* (%)	ε_0 (%)
T300	4250 (350)	30	10	4.4 (0.6)	2860 (220)	1.00 (0.06)	0.51 (0.07)
	4440 (430)	60	4	3.0 (0.6)	2630 (150)	0.93 (0.05)	0.44 (0.05)
T300-B4C	3600 (470)	30	8	3.1 (0.6)	2600 (270)	0.91 (0.09)	0.37 (0.07)
	3710 (90)	60	4	2.4 (0.3)	2510 (180)	0.89 (0.07)	0.34 (0.02)

Table 2 Weibull parameters estimated from bundle tests values and standard deviation ()

N°	N_1	m	$\langle\sigma\rangle$ (MPa)	ε^* (%)	ε_0 (%)
1	4200	3.9	3050	1.08
2	4430	4.5	2770	0.99	0.56
3	4770	4.5	2640	0.94
4	4340	3.7	2690	0.95	0.44
5	4740	3.3	2550	0.90	0.44
6	3650	4.6	2880	1.03	0.60
7	3800	5.4	2850	1.03	0.59
8	4100	4.7	2980	1.06	0.47
9	3970	4.2	2900	1.03	0.49
10	4020	4.9	3320	1.02
Mean value (Standard deviation)	4250 (350)	4.4 (0.6)	2860 (220)	1.00 (0.06)	0.51 (0.07)

Table 3 Detailed data for T300 bundle tests with 30mm gauge length

-There is good accordance between $\langle\sigma\rangle$ values obtained by the two tests (monofilament or bundle), which are slightly lower in the case of bundle experiments. This can be explained by the fact that, in this case, there is no arbitrary selection of the fibers. Moreover, the m values are very coherent in the case of monobundle experiments, whereas an abnormally high value is obtained in the case of monofilament experiments for T300 fibers with a 60mm gauge length.

This leads us to conclude to the existence of sampling problems in the case of monofilament tests.

As shown in table 3, the low dispersion of values obtained in the case of monobundle experiments, provides us with a valuable characterization of the reinforcement after a minimal number of experiments (3 or 4).

It must be underlined that the analysis of the mechanical behaviour of the fibers through the values of $\langle\sigma\rangle$ and m alone does not allows us to detect the behaviour differences of these two kinds of bundles. Indeed, the m variation which is due to these different kinds of behaviour cannot be

detected in the case of monofilament experiments, owing to the variation of this parameter with sampling conditions.

The knowledge of the ϵ_0 value and more generally the behaviour of the bundles of fibers at low strains may be however essential for understanding the mechanical behaviour of composites reinforced with these fibers. Table 4 gives the rupture strength of Al-55%T300 and Al-55%T300-B4C composites elaborated by the squeeze-casting technique. The mean initial rupture strength of fibers is given and also its value after preheating, immediately before infiltration, at 700°C during 30 minutes in an industrial nitrogen atmosphere containing a low content of oxygen. It can be seen that the rupture strength of T300 fibers decreases drastically, due to the chemical reaction of carbon with the residual oxygen. The ruture strength of T300-B4C fibers on the other hand, remains the same, owing to the B4C coating which protects the fibers from oxydation.. However, the rupture strength of T300-B4C composites is lower than that of T300 composition. This result cannot be attributed to a more extensive chemical degradation of coated fibers during infiltration.

	Fibers			Composite
	$\langle\sigma\rangle$ initial (MPa)	ϵ_0 (%)	$\langle\sigma\rangle$ preheat (MPa)	σ_R (MPa)
T300	2860	0.5	1600	350
T300-B4C	2600	0.34	2760	300

Table 4 Comparison of mechanical properties of loose bundles and composites

Tansmission and scanning electron microscope studies [9] have shown :

-That this coating does not react wıth liquid aluminium and plays an effective role as a diffusion barrier against the chemical degradation of carbon fibers.

-That composites failure is brittle and thus, owing to the high volume fraction of reinforcement, is initiated by the correlated failure of adjacent fibers. This failure mechanism (LLS mechanism [10]) is due to the fact that the failure of one isolated fiber will increase the stress only on the adjacent ones.

In these conditions, whereas the low mechanical properties of T300 composites may be explained by the chemical degradation of fibers during preheating and infiltration, it is the failure of the weakest fibers which will govern the failure strength the T300-B4C composite. The particular behaviour of coated fibers, which is well evidenced by bundle tests, may thus explain the unexpected low mechanical properties of these materials.

CONCLUSION

The comparative study of reinforcement characterization by mean of monofilament or loose bundle tests demonstrates the interest of monobundle tests. The experimental procedure set up needs only an additional determination of the modulus of the fibers for the determination of Weibull characteristics. It is thus possible to obtain a valid characterization of the reinforcement

by means of a low number of experiments. Moreover, this kind of experiment is more representative as no particular selection of the fibers is carried out, and as results represent the average behaviour of a great number of fibers, which is statistically more representative. In addition to the determination of the Weibull parameters, P- ϵ curves give valid information on the lowest rupture strain of the fibers, which may help the understanding of the mechanical behaviour of brittle composite materials.

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